

ARC

ARCHITECTURE REPRESENTATION COMPUTATION

INFORMATION VISUALIZATION

PEDAGOGICAL ENVIRONMENTS

ENERGY INFORMATION SYSTEMS

DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION

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ARC

Architecture. Representation. Computation

ARC is a multidisciplinary research group dedicated to the design, development and application of information and communication technologies (ICT) to architecture in different areas, including education, design and construction. The group was founded in 1999, and in 2009 it was officially recognized as research group by AGAUR, an education and research agency of the Catalan government. During this time, ARC has carried out numerous educational and research projects whose results have been published in international journals and presented at international conferences.

Research lines

Currently, the group has four lines of research:

DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION:

Building information modeling (BIM), modular construction and manufacturing, simulation, design and construction processes, and component catalogues (product modeling).

ENERGY INFORMATION SYSTEMS:

Development of ontologies for information systems in buildings and urban environments.

PEDAGOGICAL ENVIRONMENTS:

Collaborative learning environments and digital libraries.

INFORMATION VISUALIZATION:

Interactive interface design, information visualization, concept maps and data mining.

NETWORKING: SPACE

An abstract machine to generate spatial hypernarratives

NETWORKING SPACE is an *interactive installation* that allows users to explore the relationships between space and text. The system is designed to induce visitors' active participation by the combined actions of visual stimuli and texts. *Spaces and words are the building blocks with which spatial narratives are built in collaboration.* The installation consists of two screens: one showing spaces depicted as sequences of animation frames, and another where users interact with the selected space. Once a space is chosen, users can respond to the impressions they receive from perceiving the space by associating concepts with the animation frames. Likewise, a user can react to the words previously associated by other users. In this way, the installation allows users to explore the spatial dimension of language and the narrative dimension of space.

www.salleurl.edu/arc/netspace_sl/

SOCIAL MEDIA

Analysis in social networks

Development of a visualization and analysis tool of user activities in social networks. An dedicated interface enables the continuous adaptation of the tool functionalities to the changing structure of the data sources. The type of visualization can be customized by the analyst. Social analysis techniques are used to capture viralization processes which are represented by graphs and tree maps.

The project is funded by the program Cémit, "Social Media: Methods and Technologies for Social Media".

OIKONTOLOGY

Semantic Data Search

OIKONTOLOGY is a Linked Data browser which enables end-user exploration and data querying of the databases of the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus. There are three separated databases whose contents have been translated onto an ontology in order to facilitate integrated access to the data: OIKODOMOS Workspaces, OIKODOMOS Case Repository and OIKOPEDIA. OIKONTOLOGY provides three basic tools to retrieve data using semantic queries:

SEARCH. The search input is a single term.
Example: *What is “flexibility”?*

RELATE. The search inputs are two terms included in the ontology. The search returns all the terms which are nodes in the paths connecting both input terms.
Example: *What has “flexibility” to do with “housing”?*

QUERY. This is a syntactic search guided by the ontology structure. The input is a phrase which is built with two elements: words and properties. Words are ontology classes which are connected by properties. The query returns phrases with the same structure as the search.
Example: *Which architects have designed buildings located in the city (Barcelona)?*

www.oikodemos.org/oikontology

OIKONET

Semantic Data Search

OIKONET is a network supported by the Lifelong Learning Programme of the European Union. The objective of OIKONET is to create a platform of collaboration to study contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today's societies: architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social.

OIKONET will intertwine three areas of activity:

1. Research on housing studies from a multidisciplinary approach and a global dimension;
2. Participatory actions to engage communities in the definition, solution and evaluation of housing problems; and
3. Educational activities that integrate different actors (students, teachers, professionals, citizens) in learning spaces that combine classroom activities with those that take place in the virtual campus OIKODOMOS.

Thirty-four organizations in Europe and around the world participate in the three year project, including universities, research organizations, local administrations, as well as professional, social and cultural associations.

www.oikonet.org/

SDR:NETWORKING

Web learning environment to promote interdisciplinary teaching and participatory education

This is a web-based collaborative learning environment which has been specifically designed for the course on *SDR Systems of Representation*. The environment is divided into six distinct areas, each dedicated to the six subjects covered by the course: Text, Figure, Image, Object, Space and Light. In the Text subject, students use *concept maps* to collaboratively analyze texts about architectural theory; in the Figure subject, they make *variations of the color compositions* created by other students; in Image, the entire class contributes to creating a digital library of photographs from which ideas are derived to create photomontages; in Space, students collaboratively construct *spatial narratives*; and in Light, spaces are transformed by changing the lighting conditions. Altogether, these environments and their associated pedagogic methodology contribute to creating an innovative collaborative and interdisciplinary learning space which arises from the integration ICT in teaching architectural education.

www.salleurl.edu/sdr/info

In 2010, the Government of Catalonia awarded the SDR course the "Vicens Vives" distinction for excellence in university education in recognition of the use of ICT to overcome the boundaries between disciplines.

IN_SPACE

Giving form to space

IN-SPACE is a web-based modeling tool specifically designed to *develop the capacity to give form to space*. At the outset, the user is placed within a cubic cell at the center of a three-dimensional grid. From this starting position, *the space is modeled as the viewer moves along one of the six axes of a Cartesian space*. As the user moves, the bounding surfaces expand along the six directions. Conversely, a space can contract as the bounding surfaces moves towards the viewer. The color and lighting of surfaces can be edited, and texts and images can be attached to them. The space generated by a user can later be explored by other users following automatically-generated animation paths.

www.salleurl.edu/arc/in_space

ILLA MYRURGIA

Participatory analysis of the urban environment

This is a web environment that allows students of architecture and urban planning and citizens to collaborate in analyzing the urban environment through texts, images and videos. It consists of three areas:

1. a public environment where citizens, experts and non-experts can present and discuss their ideas about the city;
2. a restricted environment where students can analyze and discuss the ideas formulated by citizens and group them into thematic areas; and
3. a communication space where *students and citizens can exchange their points of view*, building collaborative lines of argument.

www.salleurl.edu/illamyurgia

OIKODOMOS: Workspaces

Collaborative learning based on sequences of learning activities

This learning environment is part of the platform created for the *OIKODOMOS virtual campus*. Its objective is to provide teachers and students of participating institutions a tool to design and implement learning activities which foster the *collaborative construction of knowledge*. Learning activities are structured as sequences which together make a learning workspace. As a course progresses, the learning activities designed by teachers become connected to each other. In this way, the outputs of a learning process carried out in one school might become the input for another process taking place at a different school. Learning outcomes are evaluated using rubrics containing the specific competences that students develop in a given learning activity. Learning takes place both in courses and seminars held at each institution and in the space provided by the virtual environment (blended learning).

www.oikodomos.org

OIKODOMOS was co-funded by the European Union's Longlife Learning Programme 2007-2009 and 2010-2011.

IMAGENET

Collaborative construction of knowledge from images

IMAGENET is a *web learning environment that allows a group of users to create a library of images in order to collaboratively reflect on their meanings*. Along with images, users build a vocabulary of concepts to explain their meaning. Concepts are used to establish relationships between images. Images that share certain characteristics according to users' perceptions are organized in groups.

www.salleurl.edu/arc/imagenet.htm

BCN REFLEXIONS

Images of the contemporary city

This publication consists of an *interactive web environment and a book containing the work done by students of the sDR Systems of Representation course dedicated to analyzing the contemporary city by means of photographs and photo-montages*. A digital library contains the photographs taken, described and commented on by students. Images can be grouped in various ways according to theme or subject. In the book, the images are organized into groups and routes that the readers can trace following their own associations. Both the book and the web environment share a structure which enables the reader of the book and the Internet user to *reflect on the contemporary city based on the relationships between images and concepts*.

www.bcnreflexions.net

HOUSING@21.EU

Emerging forms of housing and living in 21st century

HOUSING@21.EU is an educational platform devoted to studying housing at European level. A digital library of housing case studies has been created to support collaborative learning activities. Students and teachers from five European schools of architecture have participated in the documentation and analysis of the projects. The result of this collaborative effort is a repository containing more than 300 projects and 5,000 images which together constitute a valuable learning resource which can be expanded over time. Also, to facilitate the joint development of architectural designs by groups of students from different schools, a learning environment has been created that allows students to collaborate throughout the design process, from the early conceptual stage to the presentation final.

This project has been selected as an example of best practices by the report Bildung für eine Nachhaltige Entwicklung in den EU-Bildungsprogramme, Anne Busch, Universität Lüneburg, UNESCO, 2007.

www.housing21.eu.net

HOUSING@21.eu was co-funded by the Erasmus Intensive Programme 2003-2006.

OIKODOMOS: Case repository

Digital repository of housing projects

This repository is part of the technological platform developed for the virtual campus OIKODOMOS. It is a digital library that contains housing projects documented by students of the European architecture schools participating in the program. The description of a project includes texts, images, references, links, comments, tags (folksonomies) and key concepts (ontologies). Projects with common characteristics are grouped into collections. The contents of the library can be integrated into free-form documents and merged with other external data. Students and teachers can carry out collaborative learning activities using the resources in the repository. Following a validation process to verify the quality of their contributions, their work becomes part of the repository.

www.oikodomos.org

OIKODOMOS is co-funded by the European Union's Longlife Learning Programme 2007-2009 and 2010-2011.

BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM

Collaborative design and construction of multifamily housing units with industrial methods

BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM is a system for generating multifamily housing units built with industrial methods. Housing units are created from the aggregation of spatial bars. A rule-based system generates all the possible space solutions. The buildings are created by assembling housing units within a support structure. The generative process takes into account building regulations regarding distances to staircases, determines the optimal spaces for the building services and verifies that there are no conflicts between them and the structural elements. The facades are composed interactively by assigning values to parameters such as orientation, cost, color and proportion of glazed surface. Working drawings and bills of quantities of the buildings generated are automatically produced. A three-dimensional model of the building is also automatically generated and displayed in the system's web environment. Based on this prototype, during the period 2005-2009 a new system was developed that allows different actors (residents, technicians, developers, builders, manufacturers) to collaborate throughout the phases of design, construction and use of the housing units.

www.barcodehousing.net

BARCODE SYSTEM HOUSING was funded by the Spanish National RDI Plan 2005-2009.

BAUKOM

Catalogue of structural components based on BIM technology.

The **BAUKOM** research project has been co-funded by the “Plan Avanza, Acción Estratégica de Telecomunicaciones y Sociedad de la Información” within the “Plan Nacional de Investigación Científica, Desarrollo e Innovación Tecnológica” 2010-2013.

The aim of **BAUKOM** project is to create an on-line catalogue of precast concrete structural components –which can be enhanced to other building components- based on BIM technology to improving design, manufacture and marketing processes. The catalogue provides the necessary functionalities for the various agents involved in the processes of design and construction of a building -manufacturers, architects, consultants, contractors- to define the products and services associated with them, to access product information in formats that can be inserted in a BIM models, and to request specific services (costs, pre-dimensioning, energy consumption) to a product supplier.

OPTIMUS

Optimising the energy use in cities with smart decision support systems

“Optimising the energy use in cities with smart decision support systems (OPTIMUS)” is a research project funded by the 7th Framework Programme of the European Union (2013-16). Its goal is to design, develop and implement a Decision Support System (DSS) to help city authorities to optimize the energy use in their premises and reduce CO2 emissions.

OPTIMUS will provide an ICT platform that will collect and structure data sets from different domains: weather conditions, social web, buildings’ energy profiles, energy prices and energy production. OPTIMUS will use semantic technologies so as to combine and analyze the integrated data and propose short- term energy optimization plans in pilot cases located in Savona (Italy), Sant Cugat del Vallès (Spain) and Zaanstad (The Netherlands).

www.optimus-smartcity.eu/

Building list:

- Building X (location)
 - Energy systems: ...
 - Surface: 1423 m2
 - Floor: 4
 - Location: ...
 - Address: Via Vercellina 1
 - GPS coordinate: 44.307162, 8.481746
 - Bill: ...
 - Energy rating: G
 - Electrical energy systems: PV plant (201KW)
 - Connection with external grid
 - Thermal energy systems: ...
 - Condensing boilers fed by natural gas (200kW)
 - Volume: 22.238 m³
 - Building Y (location)
 - Building Z (location)
 - Building W (location)
 - ...

Heating and cooling system

Filter: <no selected> Days: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Action Plan: Pre-Heating schedule based on forecast

Description: Control of pre-heating/cooling of the rooms based on schedules and weather forecasts

Zone: P3 Temperature: DHW Sys.: BOILERXXXX

Starting day: < > 20/10/2014 today **22F** Type: Electricity

Search: Similar weeks

Baseline:

	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat	Sun	
	ON	OFF	ON	OFF	ON	OFF	ON	OFF
Timetable	6:30	21:00	6:30	21:00	6:30	21:00	6:30	21:00
Standard	185,60 €	178,60 €	174,60 €	181,60 €	188,60 €	135,60 €	145,60 €	1.831,20 €
Consumption (kWh)	1560	1500	1560	1470	1510	1190	1160	10.120,00
CO2 emi. (tCO2e)	0,480	0,460	0,480	0,460	0,480	0,360	0,460	5,4

Alternative 1: Economic and Green

	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat	Sun	saving
Timetable	7:00	20:00	6:50	20:20	7:00	6:50	20:20	7:00
Standard	18,00 €	17,00 €	17,00 €	16,20 €	16,30 €	15,10 €	16,00 €	100,00 €
Consumption (kWh)	150	135	147	111	100	130	116	900
CO2 emi. (tCO2e)	0,040	0,044	0,040	0,033	0,030	0,035	0,04	0,3

Alternative 2: Comfortable

	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat	Sun	saving
Timetable	6:45	20:45	6:50	20:30	6:50	6:45	20:45	6:45
Standard	18,00 €	17,00 €	17,00 €	16,20 €	16,30 €	15,10 €	16,00 €	70,00 €
Consumption (kWh)	150	135	147	111	100	130	116	900
CO2 emi. (tCO2e)	0,028	0,027	0,030	0,032	0,030	0,035	0,04	0,2

Results:

View

Electricity Energy cost (€/day)

Energy building consumption (kWh/day)

SEMANCO

Semantic tools urban planning

The SEMANCO research project is co-funded by the FP7 “ICT systems for Energy Efficiency” program of the European Union. It began in September 2011 and will last three years. There are nine partner organisations working on the project from Denmark, Germany, Italy, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom. This research consortium includes universities, community organisations, an IT developer and an environmental consultant. The project is coordinated by ARC Enginyeria i Arquitectura La Salle.

SEMANCO’s purpose is to provide semantic tools to different stakeholders involved in urban planning (architects, engineers, building managers, local administrators, citizens and policy makers) to help them make informed decisions about how to reduce CO₂ emissions in cities. To define the scope and purpose of the methods and tools to be developed in the project, SEMANCO will carry out requirements analysis in three case studies, in Spain, Denmark and United Kingdom.

www.semanco-project.eu

SEMANCO
SEMANTIC TECHNOLOGIES FOR CARBON REDUCTION IN URBAN PLANNING

Co-funded by the European Commission within the 7th Framework Programme

Home | Construction | Project | News | Publications | Publications | Contact | National projects | About | Downloads | Media | FAQ | **OBJECTIVES**

Introduction | Purpose | Objectives | Methodology | Services | Impact

The objectives of SEMANCO are to:

- Develop sustainable strategies to significantly reduce CO₂ emissions through city
- Integrate energy-related data according to the Open Data initiative and the Open standards
- Develop a semantic-based energy information framework to support decision-making
- Apply automatic data analysis processes to support energy analysis and visualization tools
- Provide available and transparent methods of measuring energy performance
- Integrate energy analysis, visualization and information tools and techniques
- Determine the value of decision support tools in terms of their CO₂ effectiveness
- Develop generalised guidelines for urban planning and redevelopment process.

Case Study: Maastricht Spain
Planning in the city of Maastricht, where major urban developments are ongoing. Maastricht is the capital of the region of Limburg, located in the geographic centre of Europe, with a population of 150,000.
Step 1 US | Maastricht

Case Study: Copenhagen Denmark
Planning on the North Harbour development located in the biggest Northern European development plan in recent years. When fully developed, the area will accommodate 40,000 residents and 40,000 work places.
Step 1 US | Maastricht

Case Study: Newcastle United Kingdom
Planning on the Riverside Quay in the Reed Bank of Newcastle, which is one of the most planned areas in the north east of England. Newcastle Quay has been identified as a key area for investment in Newcastle City Council regeneration plan.
Step 1 US | Maastricht

Photo 1 | Behind video | News & Events | Share this

SEIS

Semantic Energy Information System

SEIS – SEMANTIC ENERGY INFORMATION SYSTEM facilitates access to energy information using semantic web technologies. The system has been developed within the research project RÉPENER (BIA-2009-13365) which has been carried out from 2010 to 2013 with the support of the National RDI plan funded by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness. The data integrated in SEIS encompass energy certificates, building descriptions, energy simulations, energy performance monitoring, and climate data.

SEIS provides qualified information to different agents –such as public administrations, architectural or engineering firms, energy consultants and energy service company (ESCO)– to enable them to improve their decision-making process through the different stages of the building lifecycle –from design to construction and refurbishment. Users can retrieve and upload data in interaction with the system and can use the available services to access the data they need.

www.seis-system.org

SEIS
A Semantic Energy Information System to integrate building energy data

laSalle ARQ
Architectural Research Unit

HOME | DATA SOURCES | LINKED DATA | GLOSSARY | PREVIEW | TEAM | **Energy your data**

The objective of **RÉPENER** is a project co-funded by the Spanish National RDI Plan 2010-2013. It has been to design and implement a prototype of an information system which facilitates access to energy information using semantic web technologies. SEIS – Semantic Energy Information System provides qualified information to different agents to enable them to improve the decision-making process in their respective realms –from design to construction and refurbishment– as well as the methodologies to analyse it.

In SEIS, users with different profiles can retrieve and upload data in interaction with the system and they can invoke services operating with that data. This represents the first step in the creation of a more comprehensive energy system with additional data and services.

Design Team	Facilities Manager	Building Owner	Energy Consultant
Project of a new building Project of building retrofit Feasibility study Energy certification ...	Benchmarking Building operation Research	Building retrofit Building maintenance Benchmarking	Energy and comfort modelling Energy and comfort monitoring ...

There are four types of energy information services which have been implemented in SEIS: to provide examples of energy efficient buildings, to facilitate performance benchmarks, to identify energy efficient design patterns, and to upload building emissions. Each service is customized to the needs of four user profiles: design team, facilities manager, building owner and energy consultant.

Please see the **RÉPENER** to have an overview of the functionalities of the prototype.

The SEIS energy information system can be enhanced with near data sources. If you are a **public administration, an architectural or engineering firm, an energy consultant or an energy service company (ESCO)** you could provide data about energy certificates, building descriptions, energy simulation outcomes or energy monitoring which will be incorporated to the system.

The data available through the system can be used by energy consultants, public administrations, energy certification companies, and construction companies to develop **services** to enhance their **business opportunities**.

If you are interested to provide data to the system or to develop and market its services, please contact info@seis-system.org.

SEIS has been developed from 2010 to 2013 by **ARC Enginyeria i Arquitectura La Salle** within the research project **RÉPENER**.
It has been funded by the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness through the Spanish National RDI Plan (BIA-2009-13365).

SEIS is co-funded by the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness through the Spanish National RDI Plan (BIA-2009-13365).

REPENER

Monitoring and improving buildings energy efficiency using repositories

The objective of this project is to design and implement a prototype for a digital repository for storing, accessing and analyzing *buildings' energy performance data to improve energy efficiency*. Users of the repository will be the technical teams accessing information that will facilitate their energy analysis of buildings, in both the design of new buildings and the maintenance and monitoring of existing ones. The repository will store different types of data, both static (geometry, technical equipment, materials) and dynamic (consumption, occupation, and climate). From their combination, simulated and real data energy patterns – i.e., *simplified models of the building and its behavior*– will be produced.

The structure of the database is flexible and adaptable to facilitate its growth and sustainability to over time. The repository includes basic features to transform data into information and knowledge in specific areas, such as supporting statistical studies of the energy performance of existing buildings, formulating optimization criteria, determining reference models (benchmarking) and comparatively analyzing real and simulated scenarios.

These functionalities will be verified in different scenarios, including the design of a residential building, *predictions of consumption* in existing buildings and statistical analysis to be used in urban planning. The end result of the project is the creation of a prototype repository and n associated working methodology which can subsequently be applied on a larger scale.

REPENER is funded by the Spanish National RDI Plan 2009-2012.

INTUBE

Intelligent Use of Buildings' Energy Information

INTUBE is a research project coordinated by VTT Finland consisting of 12 groups, including research centers, universities and companies. The goal of INTUBE is to develop *tools for measuring and analyzing building energy profiles* based on user comfort needs. These tools will offer efficient solutions for better energy use and management within buildings over their lifecycles. *Intelligent Building Management Systems* will be developed to enable real-time monitoring of energy use and optimization. Neighborhood Management Systems will be developed to support efficient energy distribution across groups of buildings. They will support timely and optimal energy transfers from building to building based on user needs and requirements. *New Business Models* will be created to make the best use of the Management Systems developed. The results of INTUBE are expected not only to enhance the comfort levels of buildings' users but also to reduce overall energy costs through better energy efficiency. These results will be demonstrated in at least three pilot cases: publicly-subsidized housing in Spain, office buildings in Finland and a third case defined during the project.

www.intube.eu

IntUBE is co-funded by the 7th Framework Programme of the European Union 2008-2011.

Partners in research projects:

HOCHSCHULE FÜR TECHNIK. STUTTGART, GERMANY / FRAUNHOFER INSTITUTE FOR HUMAN FACTORS AND TECHNOLOGY MANAGEMENT. UNIVERSITY OF STUTTGART, GERMANY / HOGESCHOOL VOOR WETENSCHAP & KUNST SINT LUCAS. BRUSSELS, GHENT, BELGIUM / FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE. SLOVAK UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY. BRATISLAVA, SLOVAKIA / UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE CATALUNYA. BARCELONA, SPAIN / VTT TECHNICAL RESEARCH CENTRE. FINLAND / CSTB CENTRE SCIENTIFIQUE ET TECHNIQUE DU BÂTIMENT. FRANCE / INSTITUT D'URBANISME. UNIVERSITÉ PIERRE MENDÈS. GRENOBLE, FRANCE / TNO NETHERLANDS ORGANISATION FOR APPLIED SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH. THE NETHERLANDS / UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK. DEPARTMENT OF CIVIL & ENVIRONMENTAL ENGINEERING. IRELAND / UNIVERSITÀ POLITECNICA DELLE MARCHE. ANCONA, ITALY / SINTEF GROUP. NORWAY / POLITECHNIKA BIALOSTOCKA. POLAND / UNIVERSITY OF LIVERPOOL. SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE. LIVERPOOL, UNITED KINGDOM / CENTRE FOR CONSTRUCTION INNOVATION & RESEARCH. UNIVERSITY OF TEESIDE. UNITED KINGDOM / UNIVERSITÀ DELLA SVIZZERA ITALIANA. LUGANO, SWITZERLAND / AALBORG UNIVERSITY. DENMARK / UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE. SERBIA / CITY OF BRATISLAVA. BRATISLAVA, SLOVAKIA / BRANDENBURG UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY. GERMANY / BIALYSTOK UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY. POLAND / BULGARIAN UNION OF HOMEOWNERS ASSOCIATIONS. BULGARIA / CHALMERS TEKNISKA HÖGSKOLA AB. SWEDEN / DUBLIN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY. DUBLIN, IRELAND / EÖTVÖS LORÁND TUDOMÁNYEGYETEM. HUNGARY / UNIVERSIDAD POLITÈCNICA DE VALENCIA. VALENCIA, SPAIN / FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE SLOVAK UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY. SLOVAKIA / FACULTAD DE ARQUITECTURA Y URBANISMO, UNIVERSIDAD DE CHILE. CHILE / FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE VSUACE. RUSSIA / GEBZE YÜKSEK TEKNOLOJİ ENSTİTÜSÜ - FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE. TURKEY / HERISCAPE - HERITAGE AND LANDSCAPE, TRAINING AND CONSULTING. BOLOGNA, ITALY / UNITED NATIONS HUMAN SETTLEMENTS PROGRAMME / INSTITUTE FOR HOUSING AND URBAN DEVELOPMENT STUDIES. THE NETHERLANDS / ISCTE-LISBON UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE. PORTUGAL / ISTANBUL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY. TURKEY / KU LEUVEN - FACULTEIT ARCHITECTUUR. BELGIUM / NORWEGIAN SOCIAL RESEARCH. OSLO, NORWAY / PRAVNI FACULTET. BELGRADE, SERBIA / RIGA TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY - FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE AND URBAN PLANNING. RIGA, LATVIA / SOSTRECÍVIC. BARCELONA, SPAIN / UNIVERSITY OF CENTRAL LANCASHIRE - SCHOOL OF BUILT AND NATURAL ENVIRONMENT. LANCASHIRE, UNITED KINGDOM / UNIVERSITY OF CYPRUS. ARCHITECTURE, CYPRUS / FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE, UNIVERSITY "SS. CYRIL AND METHODIUS". SKOPJE, MACEDONIA / UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI - FACULTY OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING. LJUBLJANA, SLOVENIA / UNIVERSITÉ PIERRE MENDÈS. GRENOBLE, FRANCE / POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY OF PUERTO RICO - FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE. PUERTO RICO / UNIVERSITÀ DELLA SVIZZERA ITALIANA. LUGANO, SWITZERLAND / SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE, UNIVERSITY OF

THESSALY. VOLOS, GREECE / ORDINE ARCHITETTI PAESAGGISTI PIANIFICATORI E CONSERVATORI DELLA PROVINCIA DI RIMINI. RIMINI, ITALY / HOGESCHOOL VOOR KUNST UND WETENSCHAP. SINT-LUCAS. BRUSSELS, BELGIUM / TEESIDE UNIVERSITY. MIDDLESBROUGH, UK / CENTRE INTERNACIONAL DE MÈTODES NUMÈRICS EN ENGINYERIA. BARCELONA, SPAIN / POLITECNICO DI TORINO. TORINO, ITALY / FACHHOCHSCHULE ALBSTADT-SIGMARINGEN. ALBSTADT-EBINGEN, GERMANY / AGENCY9 AB. STOCKHOLM, SWEDEN / AYUNTAMIENTO DE SANT CUGAT DEL VALLES. SANT CUGAT DEL VALLES, SPAIN / RAMBOLL DANMARK A/S. COPENHAGEN, DENMARK / FOMENT DE LA REHABILITACIÓ URBANA DE MANRESA SA. MANRESA, SPAIN / NATIONAL ENERGY ACTION LBG. NEWCASTLE, UNITED KINGDOM / ARISTON THERMO GROUP. FABRIANO, ITALY / POYRY BUILDING SERVICES OY. VANTAA, FINLAND / VABI SOFTWARE. DELFT, THE NETHERLANDS / FACULTY OF BUSINESS AND COMPUTER SCIENCE. HOCHSCHULE ALBSTADT-SIGMARINGEN, GERMANY / NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS. NTUA. ATHENS, GREECE / ICLEI EUROPEAN SECRETARIAT GMBH. GERMANY / FUNDACIÓN TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION. SPAIN / D'APPOLONIA SPA. ITALY / UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI GENOVA. GENOVA, ITALY / COMUNE DI SAVONA. ITALY / SENSE ONE TECHNOLOGIES. GREECE / GEMEENTE ZAAANSTAD. NETHERLANDS